

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LAMIACEAE MARTINOV, NOM. CONS. (= LABIATAE JUSS., NOM. CONS.) STACHYS L.

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Abstract

Mountain-xerophyte vegetation covers more than 50% of the territory of Garagush Mountain, one of the highest peaks of the Daralayaz range. *Stachys inflata* Benth., *Stachys lavandulifolia* Vahl. (S. boissieri Kapell.) and *Stachys rhomboidalis* Grossh. belonging to the genus *Stachys* L. of the family *Lamiaceae* Martinov, nom. cons. (= *Labiatae* Juss., nom. cons.) in the formation of mountain - xerophyte (frigana) vegetation also participates.

The species belonging to the genus *Stachys* L. grow in sunny areas with medium moisture and dry soil. It is winter-hardy. It can spread by itself. It tolerates areas with little shade. It is found in sandy and rocky areas. It is most often found in the dry rocky slopes of the mountains of Iraq, Iran and the South Caucasus. It is an alpine plant. It is a tree-like herb or subshrub. It is used in folk medicine as a medicinal plant.

Keywords: Garagush mountain, Lamiaceae Martinov, nom. cons., *Stachys* L., *S. inflata* Benth., *S. lavandulifolia* Vahl. (S. boissieri Kapell.), *S. pubescens* Ten.

Mountain-xerophyte vegetation covers more than 50% of the territory of Garagush Mountain, one of the highest peaks of the Daralayaz range. The main reason is that the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic has a severe continental climate. Since the summer is hot and dry, and the winter is harshly cold, xerophytic plants prevailed in the area. This led to the formation of mountain-xerophyte or phrygana vegetation. *Stachys inflata* Benth., *Stachys lavandulifolia* Vahl. (S. boissieri Kapell.) and *Stachys rhomboidalis* Grossh., belonging to the genus *Stachys* of the family *Lamiaceae* Martinov, are also involved in the formation of mountain xerophyte vegetation. Numerous formations and associations of this plant have been found in the area of Garagush Mountain. Various photographs of the plant were taken and analyzed (Figure 1). It is included in plant systematics as follows.

Classis: Angiospermae

Subclass: Magnoliidae

Ordo: Lamiales Bromhead

Familia: Lamiaceae Martinov, nom. cons. (= *Labiatae* Juss., nom. cons.) **Genus:** *Stachys* L.

1. *Stachys fominii* Sosn.
2. *S. inflata* Benth.
3. *S. lavandulifolia* Vahl. (S. boissieri Kapell.)
4. *S. pubescens* Ten.
5. *S. stschegleewii* Sosn.

Species of the genus *Stachys* L. grow in sunny areas with medium moisture and dry soil. It is winter-hardy. It can spread by itself. It tolerates areas with little shade. It is found in sandy and rocky areas. It is most often found in the dry rocky slopes of the mountains of Iraq, Iran and the South Caucasus. It is an alpine plant.

It is a tree-like herb or subshrub. Spreading up to 38 cm wide, the l. *S. lavandulifolia* Vahl. is 20-25 cm tall. The leaves are gray-green. Basal leaves 4-5 cm, oblong-lanceolate to oblanceolate, usually with silky hairs and entire margins. Root leaves are shorter and wider. Each of its pink flowers is 7-10 cm in size, borne on short hairy spikes covered with dense cotton threads, consisting of 2-6 florets. It blooms from late spring to early summer. In the area, the plant is found in May-June.

In the formation of the meadow bushes of Garagush Mountain, along with conifer juniperus, *Acantholimon* Boiss., *Onobrychis* Hill., *Astragalus* L., *Astracantha* Podlech, *Daphne* L., *Thymelaea* Mill., *Asparagus* L. and *Thymus* L., species belonging to the genus also play a major role *Stachys* L..

The transition to forest-shrub areas usually begins with sparse bushes. *Juniperus foetidissima* Willd., *Rhamnus pallasii* Fisch. & C.A. Mey., *Rosa canina* L., *Lonicera iberica* Bieb., *Sorbus aucuparia* L., *Berberis vulgaris* L., *Cerasus microcarpa* (C.A. Mey.) Boiss. and *Pyrus caucasica* Fed. in the formation formed by the species, cereal - herbaceous (*Stachys pubescens* Ten., *Pedicularis caucasica* Bieb., *Euphorbia marschalliana* Boiss., *Reseda lutea* L., *Achillea tenuifolia* Lam., *Verbascum cheiranthifolium* Boiss., *Scutellaria karjaginii* Grossh., *Draba bruniifolia* Stev., *Ranunculus repens* L. etc.) is involved (1, p.91).

S. lavandulifolia Vahl. It is used as a medicinal plant in folk medicine. It is known for its antidepressant and appetite stimulating effects. It is used for digestive disorders. *Stachys* species are used as herbal medicine and desert tea in Anatolia as well as Iran.

Figure 1. *Stachys lavandulifolia* Vahl.

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